

Extended Chatterjea's Fixed Point Theorem on CM-Spaces Depended on Another Function

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Abstract: In this paper, we obtain a unique fixed point result that is ,extended Chattejea's fixed point theorem on CM-Spaces depended an another function . Our result is generalization results of some of the well known existing results in this literature.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a Banach contraction mapping principle fixed point theorem is most cited one(see [4] or [6]), which asserts that if (X, ρ) is a CM(Complete Metric)- space and $A: X \rightarrow X$ is contractive mapping , that is there exists $\alpha \in [0,1)$ such that for all $x, y \in X$, $\rho(Ax, Ay) \leq \alpha \rho(x, y)$. Then A has a unique fixed point. In 1968 Kannan [5] established a fixed point theorem which is also most cited result. Subsequently many authors studied and extended and generalized these results (see for e.g. [1-3], [7-11]). In 1977, B.E.Rhodes [11] considered different types of contractive conditions and canalized the relationship among them. In 2000 Branciari [4] introduced a class of generalized metric space. In 2008 Azam and Arshad [1] extended the Kannan's fixed point theorem in this kind of generalized metric spaces. Recently ,Moradi [7] obtained a result . In this paper we obtain a result, extended Chattejea's fixed point theorem on on CM-space which depends on another function.

2. PRELIMINARIES

The following are we needed getting the main results which ar due to [7].

Definition 1.1. Let (X, ρ) be a metric space . A mapping $A: X \rightarrow X$ is said to be sequentially convergent if we have ,for every sequence $\{x_n\}$, if $\{Ax_n\}$ is convergence, then $\{x_n\}$ is also convergence. A is said to be sub sequentially convergent if we have , for every sequence $\{x_n\}$, if $\{Ax_n\}$ is convergence then, $\{x_n\}$ has a convergent sub sequence.

Definition 1.2. Let X be a nonempty set . Suppose that the mapping $A: X \rightarrow X$, satisfies

- (i) $\rho(x, y) \geq 0$ for all $x, y \in X$ and $\rho(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$;
- (ii) $\rho(x, y) = \rho(y, x)$ for all $x, y \in X$;
- (iii) $\rho(x, y) \leq \rho(x, w) + \rho(w, z) + \rho(z, y)$ for all $x, y \in X$ and for all distinct points $w, z \in X \setminus \{x, y\}$. Then d is called a generalized metric and (X, d) is a generalized metric space.

3. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1. Let (X, ρ) be a CM-Space and $A, B : X \rightarrow X$ be mappings such that A is continuous, one-to-one and sub sequentially convergent . If $\alpha \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ and

$$\rho(ABx, ABy) \leq \alpha [\rho(ABx, ABy) + \rho(ABx, ABy)] . \quad \dots$$

(1)

For all $x, y \in X$, then b has a unique fixed point . Also A is a sequentially convergent , then for every $x_0 \in X$ the sequence of iterates $\{B^n x_0\}$ converges to this fixed point.

Proof: Let x_0 be an arbitrary point in X . We define the iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$ by $x_{n+1} = Bx_n$ (equivalently $x_n = B^n x_0$) $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ using (1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Ax_n, Ax_{n+1}) &= \rho(ABx_{n-1}, ABx_n) \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(Ax_{n-1}, ABx_n) + \rho(Ax_n, ABx_{n-1})] \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_{n+1}) + \rho(Ax_n, Ax_n)] \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_n) + \rho(Ax_n, Ax_{n+1})] \\ \rho(Ax_n, Ax_{n+1}) &\leq \alpha / 1 - \alpha [\rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_n)] \\ &\leq h \rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_n), \text{ where } h = \alpha / 1 - \alpha < 1. \quad \dots \end{aligned}$$

(2)

By the same argument

$$\rho(Ax_n, Ax_{n+1}) \leq h \rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_n) \leq h^2 \rho(Ax_{n-2}, Ax_{n-1}) \leq \dots \leq h^n \rho(Ax_0, Ax_1) \dots$$

(3)

By (3) for every $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $m > n$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Ax_m, Ax_n) &\leq \rho(Ax_m, Ax_{m-1}) + \rho(Ax_{m-1}, Ax_{m-2}) + \dots + \rho(Ax_{n+1}, Ax_n) \\ &\leq [h^{m-1} + h^{m-2} + \dots + h^n] \rho(Ax_0, Ax_1) \\ &= h^n [1 + h + h^2 + \dots] \rho(Ax_0, Ax_1) \\ &\leq h^n / 1 - h \rho(Ax_0, Ax_1), \text{ letting } m, n \rightarrow \infty \text{ we get that} \end{aligned}$$

$\{Ax_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence and X is a CM-Space there exists $q \in X$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = q. \quad \dots$$

(4)

Since A is sub sequentially convergent, $\{x_n\}$ has a sub sequence. So there exists

$$p \in X \text{ and } \{x_{n(r)}\} (r = 1, 2, \dots \infty) \text{ such that } \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} x_{n(r)} = p. \quad \dots$$

(5)

Since A is continuous and $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} x_{n(r)} = p$, $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} Ax_{n(r)} = Ap$. By (5) we conclude that $Ap = q$. So

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(ABp, Ap) &\leq \rho(ABp, AB^{n(r)}x_0) + \rho(AB^{n(r)}x_0, AB^{n(r)+1}x_0) + \rho(AB^{n(r)+1}x_0, Ap) \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(ABp, AB^{n(r)}x_0) + \rho(AB^{n(r)+1}x_0, ABp)] + h^{n(r)} \rho(Ax_1, Ax_0) \\ &\quad + \rho(Ax_{n(r)+1}, Ap) \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(ABp, Ax_{n(r)}) + \rho(Ax_{n(r)-1}, ABp)] + h^{n(r)} \rho(Ax_1, Ax_0) \\ &\quad + \rho(Ax_{n(r)+1}, Ap). \text{ Letting } n(r) \rightarrow \infty \\ &\leq \alpha [\rho(ABp, Ap) + \rho(Ap, ABp)] \\ &\leq 2\alpha [\rho(ABp, Ap)] \end{aligned}$$

$\rho(ABp, Ap) \leq 0$. Implies that $ABp = Ap$. Since A is one-to-one we get that $Bp = p$. Therefore B has a fixed point. Since (1) holds and A is one-to-one, B has a unique fixed point.

Now if A is sequentially convergent by replacing $\{n\}$ with $\{n(r)\}$ we conclude that

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} x_{n(r)} = p \text{ and this shows that } \{x_n\} \text{ converges to the fixed point of } B.$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

Conclusion: Our results are general and they are the generalization results of [7].

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